

Influence of Climate Resilience Strategies on Growth of Small-Scale Enterprises in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Leyira-Neesae, Evelyn B., Nwineh, Princess L. & Temple-Elendu, Blessing (PhD)

Department of Business Education, Rivers State University Port Harcourt

Corresponding Author's Email: leyira.evelyn@rsu.edu.ng; nwineh.princess@rsu.edu.ng; blessing.temple-elendu@rsu.edu.ng

Abstract

The study examined the influence of climate resilience strategies on the growth of small-scale enterprises. Specifically, it focused on business continuity planning, product diversification, and sustainable supply chain management as key strategies that may enhance enterprise development. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which enabled the researcher to gather data from a large number of respondents and describe existing conditions without manipulating any variables. The population comprised 7,800 registered small-scale enterprises drawn from various sectors, including manufacturing, retail, hospitality, and services. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 381 was obtained, but in line with Nwankwo (2006), 500 respondents were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure fair representation. A structured questionnaire titled Influence of Climate Resilience Strategies on Growth of Small-Scale Enterprises Questionnaire (ICRSGSSEQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation, and its reliability was confirmed through the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded a coefficient of 0.86. Out of 500 distributed copies, 482 were correctly completed and analysed. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while linear regression analysis tested the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that business continuity planning, diversification of products, and sustainable supply chain management did not have significant influence on the growth of small-scale enterprises. The results showed weak relationships between the examined variables and enterprise growth, with R^2 values close to zero and p-values above 0.05. This suggests that while these strategies are present among small business owners, they do not meaningfully determine business expansion. Based on the findings, it was recommended that business owners should update their continuity plans regularly to address possible risks, conduct market research before diversifying products to align with customer needs, and strengthen supplier relationships by promoting ethical and sustainable practices that support long-term stability.

Keywords: Climate Resilience, Small-Scale Enterprises, Business Growth, Adaptation Strategies, Environmental Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Organisations are increasingly seeking ways to adapt and respond effectively to the growing challenges posed by environmental changes. Climate resilience strategies refer to diverse approaches that help prepare for growing climate threats and hazards, adapt to changing conditions, and withstand and recover from acute and chronic disruptions (White House Council on Environmental Quality, 2024). Resilience in this context means the ability to prepare for threats and hazards, adapt to changing conditions, and withstand and recover rapidly from adverse conditions and disruptions, while climate resilience includes the process of adjusting systems in response to actual and projected consequences of a changing climate (White House Council on Environmental Quality, 2024). Climate resilience strategies strengthen business continuity planning by ensuring organisations remain functional during and after climate-related disruptions.

Business continuity planning is a systematic process that focuses on ensuring the resilience and preparedness of an organisation to withstand

unexpected disruptions. It involves developing strategies, policies, and procedures that guide how an organisation continues to operate during and after a crisis. According to Alshehhi and Hamdan (2022), this process helps organisations anticipate potential threats, design effective responses, and safeguard essential functions. It promotes the establishment of preventive measures such as risk assessments, contingency strategies, and recovery plans that enable the organisation to maintain productivity and service delivery. Business continuity planning is not only about reacting to emergencies but also about building organisational strength that ensures the continued performance of vital operations, even under challenging circumstances. This planning process provides a structured approach for identifying key business areas, determining the impact of disruptions, and setting priorities for recovery. By doing so, organisations are better positioned to reduce downtime, protect assets, and sustain stakeholder confidence. Business continuity planning promotes diversification of products to

minimise risks associated with market fluctuations or operational disruptions.

Diversification of products is another important strategy that enhances business sustainability and competitiveness. It involves expanding the range of products or services offered by a business to reduce dependence on a single market or product line. Musau (2023) describes diversification as an approach through which a business explores new opportunities, introduces variations of existing products, or enters new markets to increase sales and profitability. By spreading investments and risks across different products, an enterprise can create multiple streams of income and remain stable during economic fluctuations. Diversification also stimulates innovation as businesses are encouraged to identify consumer needs, explore technological advancements, and improve existing products. This practice can help revive businesses experiencing stagnant or declining sales by reaching new customer segments and strengthening brand presence. In essence, product diversification supports long-term growth and helps businesses remain adaptable in an increasingly dynamic marketplace. Diversification of products supports sustainable supply chain management by encouraging flexibility in sourcing and production processes that enhance long-term stability.

Sustainable supply chain management, as explained by Stroumpoulis and Kopanaki (2022), represents a comprehensive approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic considerations into supply chain activities. It involves the coordination of materials, information, and financial resources across different organisations to achieve shared goals of sustainability and efficiency. The concept extends beyond traditional supply chain management by promoting responsible sourcing, reducing waste, and encouraging collaboration among partners. Sustainable supply chain management ensures that businesses operate ethically while maintaining profitability and long-term viability. It requires transparency, innovation, and continuous improvement in how resources are obtained, produced, and distributed. By embedding sustainability principles into supply chain operations, organisations can enhance reputation, reduce costs, and contribute positively to society and the environment. This approach ultimately supports steady economic performance and fosters trust among customers, suppliers, and

other stakeholders. Sustainable supply chain management promotes the growth of small-scale enterprises by fostering efficient resource use and consistent product delivery.

The growth of small-scale enterprises, according to Dapper et al. (2021), represents the progressive improvement and expansion of a business in terms of its structure, output, and market presence. It reflects the ability of an enterprise to increase its productivity, revenue, workforce, and overall capacity within a specific period. Growth can manifest through various indicators such as profitability, asset accumulation, and customer base enlargement. It often results from internal processes like innovation, good management practices, and effective decision-making. For small-scale enterprises, growth also depends on factors such as accessibility, visibility, and infrastructure, which influence their operational success and market expansion. When businesses adopt sound strategies like continuity planning, product diversification, and sustainable supply chain management, they are more likely to achieve consistent growth and stability. Therefore, the development of small-scale enterprises serves as an essential measure of business success, resilience, and contribution to economic advancement.

Statement of the Problem

Small-scale enterprises play an important role in the economic development of any society as they provide employment, support local innovation, and contribute to income generation. However, many small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis are facing challenges linked to climate-related issues such as flooding, irregular rainfall, and extreme heat. These challenges often disrupt production processes, reduce access to raw materials, and increase operational costs, which in turn affect business growth and sustainability. In recent years, there has been growing awareness about the need for small-scale enterprises to adopt climate resilience strategies that can help them cope with environmental changes. Strategies such as business continuity planning, product diversification, and sustainable supply chain management are expected to help businesses adapt and maintain steady growth despite climate risks. Unfortunately, many small-scale enterprises still struggle to implement these strategies effectively, either due to lack of knowledge, limited financial resources, or poor management practices. As a result, many of these enterprises

continue to experience low productivity, business interruptions, and reduced profitability. If these issues persist, the long-term survival and growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis may be threatened. It is therefore necessary to examine how business continuity planning, diversification of products, and sustainable supply chain management influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to influence of climate resilience strategies on growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. To examine the influence of business continuity planning on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. To determine the influence of diversification of products on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. To assess the influence of sustainable supply chain management on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How does business continuity planning influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the influence of diversification of products on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
3. How does sustainable supply chain management influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: Business continuity planning does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H₀₂: Diversification of products does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H₀₃: Sustainable supply chain management does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was suitable because it enabled the researcher to collect data from a large number of respondents at once and to describe the existing conditions without manipulating any variables. It also helped to determine how climate resilience strategies influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The population of the study consisted of 7800 registered small-scale enterprises operating within Port Harcourt Metropolis. These included small businesses in areas such as manufacturing, retail, hospitality, and services. To determine the sample size, Taro Yamane's formula was applied, which yielded an estimated sample size of 381. In line with Nwankwo (2006), who advised selecting a sample size larger than the minimum obtained from statistical calculations, a total of 500 respondents was chosen using a stratified random sampling technique. This approach ensured fair representation of all categories of small-scale enterprises, including manufacturing, retail, hospitality, and services. A structured questionnaire titled Influence of Climate Resilience Strategies and Growth of Small-Scale Enterprises Questionnaire (ICRSGSSEQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A gathered information on the demographic characteristics of respondents, while Section B contained items related to business continuity planning, diversification of products, sustainable supply chain management, and growth of small-scale enterprises. The items were designed using a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by three experts, two from Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all in Rivers State University. Their corrections and suggestions helped to improve the clarity and relevance of the items in line with the study objectives. To ensure reliability, a pilot test was conducted using 20 respondents from small-scale enterprises outside the study area. The data obtained were analysed using the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.86. This indicated that the instrument was reliable and suitable for the main study. The researcher personally distributed the

questionnaires to the respondents with the help of two assistants. The purpose of the study was clearly explained to the respondents, and they were assured of confidentiality. The completed questionnaires were collected immediately after completion to ensure a high response rate. Out of the 500 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 482 were retrieved and used for the data analysis. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation to show the level of agreement among respondents. The null hypotheses were tested using linear regression analysis at a 0.05 level of significance. For the

research questions, a mean score of 2.50 and above was accepted as agreement, while a mean score below 2.50 was regarded as disagreement. For the hypotheses, any p-value less than 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, while a p-value greater than 0.05 meant that the null hypothesis was retained.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: How does business continuity planning influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation on how business continuity planning influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	My business has a formal plan to continue operations during disruptions.	124	130	119	109	2.56	1.10	Agreed
2	I regularly assess potential risks that could interrupt my business activities.	118	122	140	102	2.53	1.08	Agreed
3	My business has backup systems in place for critical operations.	131	128	103	120	2.56	1.14	Agreed
4	I have identified alternative suppliers to ensure continuous production.	120	121	119	122	2.50	1.12	Agreed
5	My business maintains adequate insurance to manage potential risks.	124	129	126	103	2.57	1.09	Agreed
6	Business continuity planning helps to minimise financial losses during crises.	104	119	134	125	2.42	1.09	Agreed
7	I review the business continuity plan regularly.	112	130	125	115	2.50	1.09	Agreed
Grand mean						2.52	0.43	Agreed

The result from Table 1 shows the summary of mean and standard deviation on how business continuity planning influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The grand mean on business continuity planning was found to be 2.52±0.43. The result further shows that respondents agreed that their business maintains adequate insurance to manage potential risks with the mean 2.57±1.09. The result also shows that respondents agreed that their business has backup systems in place for critical operations with the mean 2.56±1.14. The result further shows that respondents agreed that their business has a formal plan to continue operations during disruptions with the mean 2.56±1.10. The result

also shows that respondents agreed that they regularly assess potential risks that could interrupt their business activities with the mean 2.53±1.08. The result further shows that respondents agreed that they have identified alternative suppliers to ensure continuous production with the mean 2.50±1.12. The result also shows that respondents agreed that they review the business continuity plan regularly with the mean 2.50±1.09. Finally, the result shows that respondents agreed that business continuity planning helps to minimise financial losses during crises with the mean 2.42±1.09.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of diversification of products on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of diversification of products on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	My business offers a variety of products to meet different customer needs.	131	108	126	117	2.52	1.13	Agreed
2	Product diversification has helped to increase customer satisfaction.	119	120	114	129	2.48	1.13	Disagreed
3	Diversifying our products has reduced business risks.	146	123	95	118	2.62	1.16	Agreed
4	I regularly research new products to introduce to the market.	131	116	115	120	2.54	1.14	Agreed
5	Diversification allows my business to remain competitive in the market.	103	125	134	120	2.44	1.08	Disagreed
6	Offering multiple products has improved my business profitability.	121	139	117	105	2.57	1.09	Agreed
Grand mean						2.53	0.45	Agreed

The result from Table 2 shows the summary of mean and standard deviation on the influence of diversification of products on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The grand mean on product diversification was found to be 2.53 ± 0.45 . The result further shows that respondents agreed that diversifying their products has reduced business risks with the mean 2.62 ± 1.16 . The result also shows that respondents agreed that offering multiple products has improved their business profitability with the mean 2.57 ± 1.09 . The result further shows that respondents agreed that they regularly research new products to introduce to the market with the mean 2.54 ± 1.14 . The result also shows that

respondents agreed that their business offers a variety of products to meet different customer needs with the mean 2.52 ± 1.13 . The result further shows that respondents disagreed that product diversification has helped to increase customer satisfaction with the mean 2.48 ± 1.13 . Finally, the result shows that respondents disagreed that diversification allows their business to remain competitive in the market with the mean 2.44 ± 1.08 .

Research Question 3: How does sustainable supply chain management influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 3: Summary of mean and standard deviation on how sustainable supply chain management influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	My business sources materials from environmentally responsible suppliers.	142	98	117	125	2.53	1.17	Agreed
2	I prioritise suppliers who follow ethical labour practices.	123	116	106	137	2.47	1.15	Disagreed
3	My business monitors the sustainability of its supply chain partners.	114	121	121	126	2.46	1.12	Disagreed
4	I maintain long-term relationships with reliable suppliers.	122	120	114	126	2.49	1.13	Disagreed
5	Sustainable supply chain practices improve the quality of our products.	131	121	132	98	2.59	1.09	Agreed
6	I ensure timely delivery of materials to avoid production delays.	137	112	111	122	2.55	1.15	Agreed
7	My supply chain practices support social and environmental sustainability.	120	134	120	108	2.55	1.09	Agreed
Grand mean						2.52	0.42	Agreed

The result from Table 3 shows the summary of mean and standard deviation on how sustainable supply chain management influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt

Metropolis. The grand mean on sustainable supply chain management was found to be 2.51 ± 0.47 . The result further shows that respondents agreed that sustainable supply chain practices improve

the quality of their products with the mean 2.59 ± 1.09 . The result also shows that respondents agreed that their business sources materials from environmentally responsible suppliers with the mean 2.53 ± 1.17 . The result further shows that respondents disagreed that they maintain long-term relationships with reliable suppliers with the mean 2.49 ± 1.13 . The result also shows that respondents disagreed that they prioritise

suppliers who follow ethical labour practices with the mean 2.47 ± 1.15 . Finally, the result shows that respondents disagreed that their business monitors the sustainability of its supply chain partners with the mean 2.46 ± 1.12 .

Testing of Hypotheses

H0₁: Business continuity planning does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 4: Summary of Regression Analysis on How Business Continuity Planning Influences the Growth of Small-scale Enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	p-value
R=.037, R ² =0.001, F=0.657, p-value=.418						
1	(Constant)	2.396	0.124		19.398	0.000
	Business Continuity Planning	0.039	0.048	0.037	0.811	0.418

a. Dependent Variable: Growth, $y=0.039x+2.396$

The result from Table 4 presents the summary of regression analysis on the influence of business continuity planning on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The hypothesis (H0₁) states that business continuity planning does not significantly influence enterprise growth. The regression results strongly support this claim, showing no meaningful relationship between the two variables. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.037$) indicates a very weak positive relationship between business continuity planning and enterprise growth. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.001$) reveals that business continuity planning explains only 0.1% of the variance in the growth of small-scale enterprises, which is negligible. The overall regression model is not statistically significant ($F = 0.657$, $p = 0.418$), as the p-value is far greater than the 0.05 significance threshold. This implies that the model does not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Examining

the coefficients, the constant term ($B = 2.396$, $p = 0.000$) is significant, suggesting that in the absence of business continuity planning, the baseline level of enterprise growth stands at 2.396. However, business continuity planning itself has a positive but insignificant coefficient ($B = 0.039$, $Beta = 0.037$, $t = 0.811$, $p = 0.418$). This means that while there is a slight positive direction, business continuity planning does not significantly predict or influence the growth of small-scale enterprises. The regression equation, $y = 0.039x + 2.396$, shows that the contribution of business continuity planning is practically minimal. Overall, business continuity planning has no significant effect on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis, leading to the retention of the null hypothesis.

H0₂: Diversification of products does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 5: Summary of regression analysis on how diversification of products influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	p-value
R=.000, R ² =0.000, F=0.000, p-value=.992						
1	(Constant)	2.494	0.117		21.354	0.000
	Diversification of Products	0.000	0.045	0.000	0.010	0.992

a. Dependent Variable: Growth, $y=0.000x+2.494$

The result from Table 5 presents the summary of regression analysis on the influence of product

diversification on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The

hypothesis (H02) posits that diversification of products does not significantly influence enterprise growth. The regression results completely support this claim, showing no relationship whatsoever between diversification and business growth. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.000$) indicates the total absence of any linear association between the variables. Likewise, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.000$) confirms that diversification of products explains none of the variance in the growth of small-scale enterprises. The overall model is not statistically significant ($F = 0.000$, $p = 0.992$), as the p-value is far above the 0.05 level of significance, suggesting that diversification has no meaningful influence on growth. Regarding the coefficients, the constant term ($B = 2.494$, $p =$

0.000) is highly significant, establishing a baseline growth level of 2.494 when product diversification is absent. However, diversification of products has a coefficient of ($B = 0.000$, $Beta = 0.000$, $t = 0.010$, $p = 0.992$), indicating a complete lack of influence. The regression equation, $y = 0.000x + 2.494$, shows that diversification contributes nothing to explaining enterprise growth. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H02) is retained, confirming that diversification of products does not significantly affect the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H03: Sustainable supply chain management does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 6: Summary of regression analysis on how sustainable supply chain management influences the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	p-value
1 (Constant)	2.656	0.126		21.129	0.000
Sustainable Supply Chain Management	-0.064	0.049	-0.059	-1.299	0.195

a. Dependent Variable: Growth, $y = -0.064x + 2.656$

The result from Table 6 presents the summary of regression analysis on the influence of sustainable supply chain management on the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The hypothesis (H03) asserts that sustainable supply chain management does not significantly influence enterprise growth. The regression results are consistent with this hypothesis, showing no significant relationship between sustainable supply chain management and enterprise growth. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.059$) indicates a very weak negative relationship between the two variables. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.004$) reveals that sustainable supply chain management explains only 0.4% of the variance in the growth of small-scale enterprises, which is extremely small. The overall model is not statistically significant ($F = 1.687$, $p = 0.195$), as the p-value exceeds the 0.05 threshold, implying that the model lacks predictive power. Examining the coefficients, the constant term ($B = 2.656$, $p = 0.000$) is significant, showing a baseline growth level of 2.656 in the absence of sustainable supply chain practices. However, sustainable supply

chain management has a negative and insignificant coefficient ($B = -0.064$, $Beta = -0.059$, $t = -1.299$, $p = 0.195$). This means that an increase in sustainable supply chain management practices is associated with a very slight and statistically insignificant decrease in enterprise growth. The regression equation, $y = -0.064x + 2.656$, indicates a negligible and non-predictive relationship. Thus, sustainable supply chain management does not significantly influence the growth of small-scale enterprises in Port Harcourt Metropolis, and the null hypothesis (H03) is retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings show that business continuity planning does not have a strong effect on the growth of small-scale enterprises. This is backed by the low correlation of $R = 0.037$, meaning there is almost no link between the two, and the p-value of 0.418, which is well above 0.05 and means the result is not reliable enough to say there is an effect. Also, the R^2 value of 0.001 points out that business continuity planning only accounts for 0.1% of changes in growth, which is too small to matter much. These results stand out when

compared to other work, like Fameso (2021), who looked at construction firms and saw that continuity practices did help with performance. Yet, they match parts of Gumel and Bardai (2023), where planning strategies did not make a big difference to success in similar settings. The results point to no real link between diversifying products and the growth of small-scale enterprises. One support for this is the correlation $R = 0.000$, showing no connection at all, along with the p-value of 0.992, far over 0.05, so we cannot say diversification plays a role. Another is the $R^2 = 0.000$, meaning it explains none of the changes in growth. This goes against some studies, such as Oyeyemi (2024), who found that spreading out products and resources did boost sustainability and performance in retail businesses. Still, it lines up with Gumel and Bardai (2023), where marketing efforts, which can tie into diversification, showed no clear effect on outcomes. The findings reveal that sustainable supply chain management does not greatly affect the growth of small-scale enterprises. This is shown by the weak correlation $R = 0.059$ and the p-value of 0.195, above 0.05, indicating no solid proof of influence. Plus, the $R^2 = 0.004$ means it only covers 0.4% of growth variations, which is very little. These outcomes differ from Iyadi and Okonji (2024), who noted that supply chain practices like alliances and sharing information did improve performance. However, they echo aspects of Igashi et al. (2023), where some supply chain links, like partnerships, did not always strengthen results when other factors were involved.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the ways in which business continuity planning, product diversification, and sustainable supply chain management impact the growth of small-scale enterprises. The results indicate that these factors do not have a substantial connection to growth. Starting with business continuity planning, the data reveals a slight positive association, yet it falls short of being significant or influential. In the case of product diversification, the analysis shows no link whatsoever between diversifying offerings and improved enterprise performance. As for sustainable supply chain management, there is a minor negative correlation suggested, but it too lacks statistical weight and does not affect growth in a notable way. Taken together, these findings lead to the acceptance of all null hypotheses, meaning that business continuity planning,

product diversification, and sustainable supply chain management do not contribute meaningfully to the expansion of small-scale enterprises. The grand means from the descriptive statistics hover around 2.5, reflecting a general agreement among respondents on the presence of these practices, but the regression models consistently demonstrate weak or absent relationships, with R^2 values near zero and p-values well above 0.05. This points to other elements, perhaps such as market conditions, access to finance, or innovation strategies, that might hold more sway over business success. For small-scale enterprises, these outcomes imply a need to reassess priorities and not rely heavily on these approaches alone for growth. Instead, owners could benefit from exploring alternative methods that align better with their specific challenges. Looking ahead, future research might delve into additional variables, like digital adoption or employee training, to uncover stronger drivers of progress. It could also involve broader samples or different methodologies to confirm or challenge these results, providing a more rounded understanding for business owners and policymakers alike.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Business owners should review and update their continuity plans regularly, ensuring that they include clear steps for dealing with possible risks such as supply shortages or financial challenges.
2. Business owners should carry out market research before adding new products, so that diversification efforts are based on customer needs and market demand rather than guesswork.
3. Business owners should build stronger relationships with reliable suppliers and encourage ethical and sustainable practices that can support consistent product quality over time.

References

- Alshehhi, M. A., & Hamdan, M. N. B. (2022). Evaluating the impact of crisis management leadership on business continuity from an Islamic perspective. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(9), 118–139.

- Dapper, E. M., Meeting, G. B., & Nwiko, L. A. (2021). Enterprise location analysis and business growth of small and medium scale businesses in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 9(3), 198–206.
- Fameso, V. O. (2021). Effect of business continuity management practices on organisational performance among construction firms in Abuja. *African Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 22(4), 1-15.
- Gumel, B. I., & Bardai, B. B. (2023). *Critical success factors (CSFs) of SMEs in Nigeria and the mediating impact of SMEDAN initiative between the CSFs and SMEs' success*. HAL Open Science.
- Igashi, M., Ringim, K. J., Bugaje, I. B., & Sambo, H. S. (2023). Supply chain management practices and SMEs performance: Role of information technology capability. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 1-14.
- Iyadi, R. C., & Okonji, E. E. (2024). Supply chain management and the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics Research*, 2(1), 1-18.
- Musau, G. K. (2023). *Growth strategies and competitive advantage among five star hotels in Nairobi City County, Kenya [Master's thesis, United States International University-Africa]*. USIU-Africa Digital Repository.
- Stroumpoulis, A., & Kopanaki, E. (2022). Theoretical perspectives on sustainable supply chain management and digital transformation: A literature review and a conceptual framework. *Sustainability*, 14(8), Article 4862.
- White House Council on Environmental Quality. (2024). *Assessing the progress and impact of federal climate adaptation: Developing climate resilience indicators and metrics*.